

PECULIARITIES OF ORGANIZING ART CLASSES IN SPECIAL SCHOOLS

Mirsaid Mukhiddinovich Murtazoev
Bukhara State University, student

Abstract. Fine art classes are considered as one of the main subjects in the educational process of auxiliary schools. Because visual arts classes serve to enrich children's artistic and aesthetic outlook. Under the influence of visual arts, children's level of emotional awareness increases, and their intellectual and willful qualities develop. Correction of hand motor skills is also performed effectively.

Key words: school, education, visual arts, lesson, science, training.

Teaching children to perceive, understand, perceive and independently think about the beauty in life and art, to develop and enrich their artistic-aesthetic imagination, worldview, to cultivate a conscious attitude to the environment and culture is the main part of visual arts. is the goal.

Visual art classes in the secondary school include the following tasks related to the artistic education of children:

- as one of the first elements of moral education in students, to develop such qualities as noticing, observing, understanding, imagining and analyzing, comparing, thinking, summarizing, mastering beautiful and elegant things;
- to teach students to observe events of social life and to form preliminary ideas about them through events depicted in works of visual art;
- to further develop students' theoretical understanding by giving them an understanding of the types of visual art training;
- to give students an understanding of the shape, structure, size, differences in appearance, well-known signs of things, to teach them to feel the sequence and color of pattern elements;
- by teaching students to make and draw different things based on different materials, to strengthen their cognitive activity and independence, to further develop their creativity and initiative;
- to educate students in the spirit of good manners, friendly attitude and mutual assistance, as well as respect for historical and national traditions - customs, rituals, traditions by means of visual arts;
- to teach to appreciate the national profession - trades;

- through visual arts, to educate students' love for the nature of their beloved country, interest in the social work of people, and a sense of respect;
- formation and development of students' artistic-aesthetic taste, ecological spirituality;
- education of artistic culture in students;
- to provide artistic education to secondary school students based on finger gymnastics, various imaging exercises, and didactic games in order to eliminate some defects;
- development of artistic and creative abilities, initiative and independence in secondary school students;
- to teach secondary school students to be able to reflect the aesthetic feelings and concepts obtained on the basis of seeing and perceiving things and events in the environment in the pictures they draw;
- development of visual and construction-making skills of students with the help of various auxiliary tools and methods;
- development of features such as visual memory, tactile ability, color perception, visual imagination in secondary school students;
- to introduce secondary school students to the fundamentals of visual and decorative - applied art, architecture, and to further expand their range of artistic thought;
- teaching auxiliary school students to apply in life the knowledge and skills they have acquired in the practical works of fine art, artistic construction - making classes;
- to develop aesthetic and emotional sensitivities in auxiliary schoolchildren to the events taking place in the environment;
- artistic construction - teaching to make various toys from cardboard and colored paper, natural and discarded materials, etc.

It requires the implementation of general tasks from the visual arts in auxiliary schools, the provision of visual aids, didactic materials, electronic textbooks and special educational films, as well as the necessary literature for teachers and students. Each of the visual arts classes is for students with mental retardation. One of the necessary conditions is that it helps to correct their shortcomings, has a positive effect on their personal qualities and general development, and enriches the range of artistic knowledge of each student. For this purpose, it is necessary to strengthen the preliminary preparatory work, to bring the process of artistic

education to students in connection with life and practice. Only then will it be possible to develop the artistic and aesthetic culture of students in a national way. Special attention is paid to didactic principles in the teaching of visual arts in auxiliary schools. It is known that the conscious acquisition of knowledge and skills from visual arts requires a certain degree of independence and activity from the student. Mentally retarded students often find it difficult to find solutions to simple questions even in higher classes. Accordingly, it is necessary to give them tasks that are as understandable as possible. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate the student to want to do the work and to have confidence in his own strength.

Demonstration is important in auxiliary school education, it allows further development of the student's perception and imagination. Mentally retarded children understand the external and internal nature of objects, events and phenomena through visualization. Through this, their thinking becomes correct. It is worth noting that it is important to develop the intuition, perception, and thinking of mentally retarded students. Because the main defect in mentally retarded children is the underdevelopment of thinking. The main shortcoming of the thinking of secondary school students is superficiality, slowness, narrowness, lack of independence. That is why it is important to make auxiliary school education simple, to provide educational materials to students in a clear and understandable way. Also, it is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that the intellectual activity and independence of mentally retarded students is somewhat low and inactive in the process of art education. The higher the organization of fine arts classes, the more this activity affects the development of the individual.

Pupils acquire various knowledge, skills and abilities from visual arts and improve their activities. If the students' visual activity was initially based on analysis, it gradually turns into independent creative expression. During the artistic-aesthetic development of the student, his artistic activity acquires a positive character based on the increasing experience of imaging. In this case, the student's visual activity gives a wide opportunity to search for new ways and directions. In the process of visual activity, students develop spiritually and artistically and aesthetically. Any of their activities becomes a socially useful activity.

In the artistic and aesthetic education of students from fine arts, national works of Uzbek painters depicting the nature, social life, and labor of people in Uzbekistan, as well as poems, stories, fairy tales, parables, paintings related to Nowruz, it will be appropriate to pay attention to the use of songs.

In order to further enrich the artistic education of students, it is useful to organize more trips to nature and museums with them, and to strengthen the organization of theatrical performances.

In the conditions of the transition to the current market relations, it is important to inculcate hard work and thriftiness in students by providing economic education from visual arts, as well as connecting them with the environment, life, nature, and practice in the implementation of ecological education. That's how visual art becomes an effective product of educational work.

The most important thing is that students should consider using the knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired from visual arts in life.

Also, it is allowed to determine, increase, decrease, and make some changes to the number of hours allocated to each subject of fine art classes based on the circumstances. When making changes, it is important to consider the knowledge, skills, and abilities that students of I-IV grades should acquire.

In the planning of subjects related to visual arts, importance was attached to the work of seasonal (for red calendar days) themed pictures, and the rules of consistency, sequence and progress from simple to complex were specially followed in the arrangement of subjects. All these useful activities allow to achieve effective success in this field.

To give students an understanding of decorative painting. To help them create pattern elements by stylizing real images (plants and fruits, geometric shapes, spatial objects, birds, animals, insects, objects, human figures, etc.) and develop the structure of pattern compositions. Also, to introduce different patterns in folk art and to teach them how to make simple patterns. Creating the ability of students to make independent patterns. To develop students' skills in creating decorative patterns for various items by creating pattern compositions from different materials; to further enrich their aesthetic sense and develop their ability to perceive.

LITERATURE.

1. Abdurazzokovna R. N., Murotdilloevna A. M. SOME ASPECTS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF THE INDEPENDENT WORK OF THE FINE ARTS STUDENTS //European science. – 2021. – №. 2 (58). – C. 83-85.
2. Murotdilloevna A. M., Abdurazzokovna R. N. MUSEUM ACTIVITIES AND TOURISM IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE //European science. – 2021. – №. 2 (58). – C. 92-94.

3. Mamurova D. I., Abdullayev S. S. Importance of decorative painting in fine art lessons in general secondary schools //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 3. – C. 32-37.
4. Pirnazarov G. F., Mamurova F. I., Mamurova D. I. Calculation of Flat Ram by the Method of Displacement //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 35-39.
5. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Directions For Improving Teaching Methods //Journal of Positive School Psychology. – 2022. – C. 9671–9678-9671–9678.
6. Aminov, A. S., Mamurova, D. I., & Shukurov, A. R. (2021, February). Additional and didactic game technologies on the topic of local appearance. In *E-Conference globe* (pp. 34-37).
7. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Information Technology in Education //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 17-22.
8. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Opportunities to use information technology to increase the effectiveness of education //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECSE). – 2022. – T. 14. – №. 02.
9. Mamurova D., Khusnidinova N. Didactic possibilities of using computer graphics programs in the educational process //BIO Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2024. – T. 84. – C. 02020.
10. Mamurova D. I., Ibatova N. I., Badieva D. M. The importance of using the keys-stadi innovative educational technology method in training the image module of geometric shapes //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 335-338.
11. Khodjayeva N. S., Yakhyayeva M. T. Calculate Exact Integrals in the Visual Basic Window of Excel //International Journal on Orange Technologies. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 172-177.
12. Khodjayeva N., Sodikov S. Methods and Advantages of Using Cloud Technologies in Practical Lessons //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 77-82.
13. Khodjayeva, Nodira. "THE URGENCY OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN PROSPECTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING." *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры* 3.5 (2023): 77-80.
14. Mamurova, Dilfuza I. "Application of advanced information technologies of training at drafting lessons." *Eastern European Scientific Journal* 6 (2018).

15. Mamurova, Dilfuza Islomovna. "The role of graphics programs in improving the learning process using information technology." *EFFLATOUNIA-Multidisciplinary Journal* 5.2 (2021).
16. Islamovna, M. D., & Maftuna, B. (2023). MAKTAB TASVIRIY SAN'AT DARSLARIDA O 'QUVCHILARNING KOMPOZITSION FIKRLASH QOBILİYATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODIKASI. *Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art*, 122-126.
17. Mamurova, D. I. (2022). TA'LIM JARAYONIDA ARCHICAD DASTURINING O'ZIGA XOS HUSUSIYATLARI HAMDA AFZALLIKLARI. *ILM-FAN TARAQQIYOTIDA ZAMONAVIY QARASHLAR: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR*, 45-47.
18. Mamurova D., Ravshanova S. FORMING STUDENTS' AESTHETIC ACTIVITY USING APPLIED ART ELEMENTS IN FINE ARTS LESSONS //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 87-90.
19. Islamovna M. D., Madina B. AMALIY BEZAK FANLARINI O'QITISHDA KOMPYUTER GRAFIKASIDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI //Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art. – 2023. – C. 127-131.
20. Khodjayeva N. S., Mamurova D. I., Nafisa A. Importance in pedagogical techniques and educational activity //International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. – 2020. – T. 5. – C. 5-5.
21. Mamurova D. I. Effectiveness of Organization of Classes of Fine Arts on the Basis of Integration //Web of Semantics: Journal of Interdisciplinary Science. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 5. – C. 474-479.
22. Djalolovich, Y. N., Kodirovich, M. D., Ruziboevich, S. A., & Islomovna, M. D. (2021). Improving the professional training of fine art teachers. *European science*, (2 (58)), 44-46.
23. Mamurova D. I. Graphics Processor and its Main Capabilities //" ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2023. – C. 53-57.
24. Islomovna, M. F., Isomjonovna, R. D., Islom, M., Sharifovna, K. N., & Islomovna, M. D. (2021). Designing the methodical system of the teaching process of computer graphics for the specialty of engineer-builder. *The journal of contemporary issues in business and government*, 27(4), 165-169.
25. Islamovna, M. D., & Gulhumor, M. (2021). Principle of teaching draft geometry and computer graphics.